

Stabilization strategies in biomass depolymerization using chemical functionalization

Ydna M. Questell-Santiago¹, Maxim V. Galkin², Katalin Barta^{2*} and Jeremy S. Luterbacher^{1*}

¹ Laboratory of Sustainable and Catalytic Processing, Institute of Chemical Sciences and Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Lausanne, Switzerland

² Stratingh Institute for Chemistry, University of Groningen, Groningen, Netherlands

*email: jeremy.luterbacher@epfl.ch k.barta@rug.nl

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Abstract

A **central feature** of most lignocellulosic biomass valorization strategies is the depolymerization of all its three major constituents: the biopolymers cellulose and hemicellulose to simple sugars, and lignin to phenolic monomers. However, the formation of reactive intermediates, generally resulting from dehydration reactions, and subsequent undesired condensation pathways during biomass deconstruction have posed fundamental challenges that have shaped current commercial solutions in biomass valorization. Recently, new strategies **have emerged with a specific focus on suppressing condensation from reactive intermediates by avoiding their formation through chemical functionalization or by stabilizing these intermediates through selective transformations.** These strategies are providing unforeseen upgrading pathways, products and process solutions. In this review, we outline the molecular driving forces that shape the deconstruction landscape and these chemical functionalization strategies, offer a perspective on further developments and the potential of these strategies to sustainably produce renewable platform chemicals.

[H1] Introduction

Lignocellulosic biomass is a promising and sustainable alternative to fossil carbon which represents the bulk of terrestrial biomass.^{1,2} Its composition includes three major biopolymers: cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Their content varies between 30–50% cellulose, 20–35% hemicellulose, and 15–30% lignin.^{2,3} The cellulose fraction is exclusively composed by **anhydroglucose units (AGU)** linked linearly via β -1,4-glycosidic bonds (Figure 1 b, 2).^{4,5} The interaction between these chains induces the formation of rigid and semi-crystalline fibers through hydrogen and van der Waals bonds, making it insoluble in most conventional solvents.^{6,7} These cellulose polymer chains can have a polymerization degree up to 10⁷ **AGU** in woody biomass.⁸ Hemicellulose is an amorphous hetero-polymer with branches and short lateral chains, **which may contain** five different types of sugars (D-galactose, D-mannose, D-glucose, L-arabinose and D-xylose), xylose being the most abundant (Figure 1 a, 1).^{9–11} The hydroxyl groups of these sugars can be partially substituted with acetyl groups and, other minor sugars such as L-rhamnose and α -L-fucose can be present. The degree of polymerization is significantly lower compared to cellulose as it varies between 50 to 300 **anhydrosugar** units.¹² Finally, lignin is also an amorphous hetero-polymer composed of methoxylated phenylpropanoid units (Figure 2, 15).^{3,13} Because of its lower oxygen content compared to cellulose and hemicellulose (30 wt% oxygen in lignin versus 49 wt% in cellulose), lignin accounts for about 40% of the biomass heating value.^{2,14}

In the plant cell wall, lignin surrounds hemicellulose and cellulose, while cellulose fibers are interlaced with hemicellulose.¹⁵ As a result, most biomass conversion routes begin with the extraction of lignin and some hemicellulose sugars for two reasons. **First, the hydrolysis reactions of hemicellulose and lignin tend to be kinetically more favorable than the hydrolysis of cellulose. Hence, most biomass deconstruction methods remove hemicellulose and lignin before extensive cellulose depolymerization.** Second, their removal increases accessibility and purity of the cellulose, which facilitates its further processing and use. Each of the monophenols or simple sugars resulting from the depolymerization of the three constituents of lignocellulosic biomass has been explored as a feedstock to replace petroleum-based products including

fuels, materials, and fine chemicals.^{16,17} However, given their structure and reactivity differences, developing integrated approaches for the conversion of all three biomass fractions into well-defined monomers or other platform chemicals is challenging.¹⁸ As we explain in detail here, lignin has been especially challenging to upgrade to well-defined platform molecules in an integrated way with cellulose and hemicellulose for which many longstanding strategies exist. As a result lignin valorization has often been ignored despite its aromatic structure that is an attractive feature for petrochemical substitution, and its low oxygen content and resulting higher energy density compared to polysaccharides.^{19,20}

The initial step of biomass conversion generally consists of the transformation of its biopolymers into single carbohydrates (e.g. **3** and **4**) from cellulose and hemicellulose, and phenylpropanoid monomers (e.g. **20**) from lignin through C—O bond cleavage.²¹ The cleavage of these C—O linkages in both polysaccharides and lignin can happen readily even in inexpensive systems through hydrolysis including just pure water (autohydrolysis) or dilute acid (pH = ~2.5).^{22–24} However, the chemical nature of the C—O bond in the glycosidic linkages (a hemiacetal) is different from those occurring in lignin ether bonding motifs (alkyl aryl ethers)²⁵, which leads to their different bond cleavage energies. These differences require targeted strategies for the stabilization of solvolytically released species to avoid subsequent acid catalyzed reactions such as dehydration, condensation and uncontrolled repolymerization, which form polymers that contain extremely recalcitrant C—C bonds known as humins for sugar-derived degradation products (**14**) and condensed or technical lignins for the lignin-derived products (**28**).^{26,27} The balance between depolymerization and degradation kinetics for these three biopolymers has always controlled the production of simple sugars and lignin monomers. Various depolymerization strategies have found ways to address these kinetic limitations. However, they often increase process costs due to the need for added, often sacrificial, catalysts or biocatalysts, which are often not fully compatible with all lignocellulose fractions. As a result, current biorefinery processes use technologies that lead to an incomplete valorization of biomass.^{28,29} Below, we discuss the kinetics of lignin and then of polysaccharide depolymerization and how these kinetics have shaped depolymerization solutions.

[H2] Kinetics of lignin deconstruction and degradation

Lignin is biosynthesized by the radical coupling between coniferyl, sinapyl, and *p*-hydroxyphenyl alcohol resulting in several interunit linkages held together by either C—C or C—O bonds or both.^{13,19} As we will cover in detail, lignin's structure is actually the most sensitive fraction under typical biomass deconstruction conditions which generally focus on cleaving C—O linkages rather than the much more recalcitrant C—C linkages. A typical hardwood lignin contains between 60 and 80% ether linkages and a typical softwood contains from 40 to 60% ether linkages, the remainder being C—C linkages (Figure 2, 15).²⁷ Because the linkages are thought to be randomly distributed, and because each monolignol must be surrounded by two ether linkages to produce a monomer, a theoretical monomer yield based on cleaving ether bond linkages can be estimated as the square of the ether linkage (i.e. those present between C₉ units) content in native lignin (Equation 1).^{19,27,30–32} To our knowledge, Yan et al.³³ were the first to develop these correlations to estimate lignin monomer and dimer yields using the amount of ether linkages in white birch. Based on this, the theoretical monomer yield is usually around 45–55% for hardwoods and 20–30% for softwoods.^{31,33,34}

$$\text{Theoretical lignin monomer yield} \approx (\text{ether linkages})^2 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where ether linkages include all the different types of pure ether linkages in lignin (Figure 2, 16) and are assumed to be randomly distributed throughout a linear polymer chain, where C₉ monomers are connected through either C—O or C—C linkages, ignoring both more complicated structures and end groups effects. This approach is based on several assumption: lignin is linear, of infinite length with only C—O or C—C bonds between monomers and that each monomer formed requires an ether linkage on both sides to be cleaved during depolymerization.³¹

The bond dissociation enthalpies (BDEs) for the various linkages in lignin range between 42 and 83 kcal·mol⁻¹ for ether linkages, and between 54 and 118 kcal·mol⁻¹ for C—C linkages (Figure 2, 15).^{27,35–37} Though these values give some indication of the difficulty of breaking C—C linkages, or ether linkages in purely thermal processes, they are not indicative of the energy required to break ether linkages in aqueous

or acidic conditions. Under these conditions, the reaction does not proceed via single-step homolytic cleavage but rather via a multi-step acid catalyzed cleavage and/or modification of the molecule.

The most abundant linkage in lignin is the β -aryl ether unit also known as β -O-4' linkage (Figure 2, 16).^{3,13,30} This linkage contains a benzylic secondary hydroxyl at the C α position and a primary hydroxyl at the C γ position. Sturgeon et al. studied a β -O-4' linkage and calculated that the activation energy in acidic conditions (E_{aH^+}) required to dehydrate the α -hydroxyl group and form a benzylic carbocation (18) was around 3 kcal·mol⁻¹ for a lignin dimer with a free phenolic OH.³⁸ This value was calculated for a model compound rather than measured for real lignin and thus is difficult to verify. However, even when considering uncertainty, the activation energy for β -O-4' cleavage, proceeding through intermediate 19 was 11 kcal·mol⁻¹, which was significantly higher. The C α -OH BDE decreases with increase of methoxylation degree (56 to 48 kcal·mol⁻¹)³⁹ and for terminal β -O-4' fragments with unprotected phenol hydroxyl group. Therefore, the barrier to modification can be higher for the middle of the lignin polymer than for end units. Intermediates 18 and 19 can undergo cleavage via either direct re-hydration and C—O bond scission, which produces Hibbert ketones in which the C3 aliphatic moiety is maintained (C3 pathway, see Scheme SI 1 in the Supplemental Information or SI). Alternatively, a deformylation step precedes the C—O bond cleavage and rehydration steps (C2 pathway) to produce C2-aldehyde species (24) that are prone to recondensation. Only Hibbert ketones can be easily measured from lignin confirming the key role of C2 aldehydes in re-condensation processes.⁴⁰

The energy barriers of lignin modification processes demonstrate how sensitive these linkages are under lignin extraction or pretreatment conditions. Reported activation energies for hemicellulose hydrolysis in acidic conditions have ranged between 18 and 50 kcal·mol⁻¹ (Figure 1 a and discussion below)⁴¹ and the activation energy for cleaving the lignin-carbohydrate linkages has been reported at 19 kcal·mol⁻¹—both of which are significantly higher than the energy required for α -hydroxyl group dehydration⁴². These differences clearly indicate that the lignin backbone will undergo modification before or faster than any

chemical extraction occurs. The challenge is that this modification is problematic. If a benzylic carbocation is formed, condensation reactions were calculated to be significantly more favorable than cleavage if free aromatic rings were presented.^{38,43} Condensation reactions can lead these fragments to rapidly form new C—C linkages, which are highly recalcitrant, thus drastically reducing possible depolymerization yields for these modified lignin structures.^{29,30,44,45} Several catalytic strategies have been proposed to cleave C—C linkages in technical lignins but these are still exploratory and will always face lower selectivity than ether cleavage in native lignin.²⁷ This competition between the cleavage of β —O—4' linkages and the more favorable formation of new C—C bonds controls upgrading yields. Despite these challenges, several strategies have been developed to fractionate biomass and extract lignin while limiting its degradation leading to isolated lignins with a wide variety of structural modifications.

[H3] Unstabilized lignin extraction

Organosolv processes can extract lignin by solvolysis. Acid-catalyzed organosolv processes feature added Brønsted (e.g., H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, HOTf, and acetic acid)^{46,47} or Lewis acid (e.g. FeCl₂, ZnCl₂, metal triflates)^{48–50}, that decreases the pH of organosolv liquor usually to the values between 2 and 4, which significantly accelerates solvolysis of the lignocellulosic matrix leading to removal of both hemicellulose and lignin. If no acid is used the pH will still decrease during the process course from 7 to approximately 4 due to deacetylation of hemicellulose (1 to 6% of hemicellulose (1) hydroxyl groups are acetylated). The degree of delignification and hemicellulose removal depends on the solvent system property, severity of the process, and nature of the acid catalyst. Delignification is quite sensitive to acidity at low temperatures (<120°C)⁵¹ but at temperatures where solvolysis reactions rapidly occur, delignification was found to not be significantly affected by the pH⁵². The cellulose fraction usually stays intact since organosolv conditions are generally too mild to cause cellulose fragmentation. As discussed above, any condition that is harsh enough to extract lignin is generally harsh enough to dehydrate the β —O—4' structure leading to the formation of C—C linkages. However, condensation reactions are not universally faster as they can be overtaken by stabilization reaction (see subsequent discussions in this review). Furthermore,

repolymerization can be minimized when the acidolysis is carried out at the mildest possible conditions and is commonly assisted by an organic solvent such as tetrahydrofuran, alcohols, 1,4-dioxane, and γ -valerolactone capable of solubilizing lignin-fragments.^{49,53-55} This technique leads to preservation of up to 62% β -O-4' linkages of the native lignin at optimal reaction conditions.⁴⁹ Nevertheless, because **aromatic monomer** yields tend to be proportional to the square of the β -O-4' ether bonds content, this still leads to a rapid drop in yield. The first fraction of lignin (typically around 30%) extracted under mild conditions can typically be depolymerized almost quantitatively but as the conditions are adjusted (either using time or severity) to extract more lignin, potential monomer yields quickly drop.⁵⁶

In the same way, the use of a flow-through reactor can prevent **both condensation reactions and/or preserve original structure of lignin** by removing anything that is solubilized from the heated zone and, therefore, rapidly dropping the reaction temperature of this fraction.^{3,57} **Anderson et al.⁵⁸ reported lignin monomer yields (20) around 4 wt% in a flow-through setup at 190 °C with MeOH, while** Samec and colleagues⁵⁹ obtained lignin monomer yields up to 21 wt% of the original Klason lignin by pumping an acidified mixture of MeOH and water through birch wood at 200 °C and rapidly dropping the temperature of the resulting solvent. **Zhou et al.⁶⁰ pumped 72 wt% aqueous formic acid solution through poplar wood allowed, which preserved up to 83% of the β -O-4' moieties (compared to MWL) with the delignification degree of around 90%.** However, the lack of stabilizing reactants generally comes at the expense of significant solvent use (1:50—1:100 biomass-to-solvent ratio) to achieve full lignin extraction at flow-through conditions, which makes product recovery a significant challenge.

[H2] Kinetics of polysaccharides deconstruction

The vast majority of polysaccharide depolymerization processes have been built around the acid hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds in cellulose and hemicellulose. This hydrolysis reaction has been frequently described by pseudo first-order sequential reaction that depends on the H_3O^+ ion concentration, the temperature, and the chemical environment of the bond.⁶¹⁻⁶⁷

The kinetic constants of these models are dependent on the acid concentration and the temperature in the system, and were represented by the following modified Arrhenius equation:

$$k_i = [A]^{n_i} k_{0,i} \exp\left(\frac{E_{a_i}}{RT}\right) \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

where i is the reaction in question (1, 2, etc.), n_i is the acid exponent (empirical exponent) and $[A]$ is the concentration of acid (often sulfuric acid).

Although the energetics of these hydrolysis models offer some useful insights into the challenges of polysaccharide depolymerization **and can be used to explain apparent kinetic trends, other phenomena can at least partially control reactions with whole biomass including mass transfer effects. More detailed analyses are required to fully account for such effects.** Because the depolymerization of hemicellulose and cellulose involves the use of heterogeneous substrates where access to reactants and diffusion can play significant roles, a huge spread in parameter estimates permeates the literature. In particular, reported activation energies ($E_{a_{H^+}}$) have ranged between 18 and 50 kcal·mol⁻¹ for hemicellulose and between 27 and 43 kcal·mol⁻¹ for cellulose (Figure 1 **a** and **b**). Despite the large spread, these values are clearly higher than the activation energy associated with lignin modification, which further emphasizes the difficulty of preventing lignin degradation during biomass deconstruction. Furthermore, the ranges of activation energies reported for hemicellulose and cellulose are usually within the same range as those of their dehydration reactions, which produce furfural (**12**) and 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF, **13**) from xylose and glucose, respectively (Figure 1 **a** and **b**). The proximity of these ranges is indicative of the challenge of producing simple sugars from cellulose and hemicellulose without further dehydration. In practice,

achieving high monosaccharide yields is much more straightforward for hemicellulose than cellulose. The reported activation energies for cellobiose and xylobiose hydrolysis in acidic conditions, which are soluble dimers of glucose and xylose are 31 and 33 kcal·mol⁻¹, respectively. The easier depolymerization of hemicellulose is due to its different heterogeneous structure and specifically to its lack of crystallinity, which makes its glycosidic bonds much more accessible to hydrolysis. The maximal monosaccharide yields for various conditions, which are dictated by the sequential reactions shown in equations 2 and 3, illustrate this difference between the two polymers. Near quantitative xylose yields from hemicellulose can be reached within minutes at temperatures below 200 °C under dilute acid conditions (≤ 3 wt%).^{22,63} In comparison, much higher temperatures (>220 °C) are required to reach reasonable glucose yields from cellulose for similar residence times and those maximal yields are much lower (<60%). Due to these differences, either dual stage hydrolysis processes or specific treatments of the cellulose fraction are usually used when trying to maximize the yield of both soluble carbohydrates, i.e. first hemicellulose at a lower temperature and then cellulose at harsher or modified conditions.

Further dehydration of sugars to furans produces highly reactive molecules that tend to rapidly condense predominantly through aldol condensation pathways to produce insoluble solid products known as humins (14).⁶⁸ Humin formation is sufficiently favorable that if furans are targeted as a product, furans need to be removed from the reactive mixture such as through selective extraction or reactive distillation.^{69,70} Humins are randomly crosslinked macromolecules with a carbon content between 50–66 wt%, containing 29–46 wt% oxygen with the rest being hydrogen.^{71,72} Because they are exclusively formed by C—C linkages the energy required for their cleavage can be approximated by their BDE, which is significantly higher than the activation energy required for cleavage of glycosidic bonds in acidic conditions. In addition, similarly to condensed lignin, the condensation process is uncontrolled and if any catalytic processes are developed to cleave these linkages, they will face selectivity issues. For this reason, humins' current use is the production of low value heat and electricity by combustion. However, several studies have explored humin

valorization to hydrogen⁷¹ or activated carbon⁷² but these strategies limit the valorization of cellulose as platform chemicals.

[H3] Cellulose depolymerization in hydrothermal and dilute acid systems

As discussed, cellulose depolymerization is challenging because the apparent activation energy for cellulose depolymerization is usually higher than that of glucose degradation leading to lower yields at lower processing temperatures (<250 °C). However, as a result, increasing the reaction temperature activates the hydrolysis more than the degradation reaction.^{22,64,73} Peterson et al. analyzed the data from many different studies to show that, because of its higher activation energy, cellulose depolymerization starts to outpace glucose degradation at around 350 °C in pure water.⁷⁴ Using the kinetic model from Equation 3 for cellulose, yields of 40% and 80% were obtained for systems at 350 and 450 °C for 1 s or 10 ms of retention time, respectively,² which is consistent with experimental data.⁷⁵⁻⁷⁷

Moreover, dilute acid hydrolysis processes can be used to combine the advantages of elevated temperature with increases in proton concentrations by addition of small quantities of acid.^{28,78} Addition of acid has the benefit of reaching the same carbohydrate yield as in the hydrothermal process at lower temperature (e.g. 60% glucose yield at 240 °C in 10 s).² Despite the technical difficulties that these systems present, mainly due to their high pressure drop and short residence time, several two-stage chemical hydrolysis processes have been commercialized.^{28,77,79-83} A larger number of processes use a single stage dilute acid hydrolysis as a pretreatment, where lignin and hemicellulose are partially depolymerized and extracted, while cellulose is often hydrolyzed by enzymes in a second step. Another approach to avoid using these harsh conditions is to decouple the depolymerization and degradation reactions using flow-through reactors. These systems can lead to high yields of sugars by rapidly removing soluble sugars from the heated zone by flowing a solvent through the solid substrate, which minimizes degradation.^{21,22,84} The kinetics are decoupled because the depolymerizing solid has a much longer residence time than the degrading soluble product, which is rapidly removed from the reactor. However, this introduces a tradeoff between product yield and

concentration, where, if a glucose yield from cellulose close to 70% is targeted, sugar concentrations are generally limited to less than 1.5 wt%.²²

[H3] Depolymerization facilitated by organic solvents

The use of organic solvents can facilitate traditional dilute acid processes in several ways. Notably, organic solvents can remove lignin much more effectively by solubilizing the extracted (usually condensed) lignin and avoiding its reprecipitation on the surface of the cellulose.⁸⁴⁻⁸⁶ Solvents, in particular polar aprotic solvents, can also enhance the activity of the acid catalyst and reduce its loading and/or lower the processing temperature.^{87,88} Increases in the activity of the acid is generally due to solvation effects in polar aprotic solvents, which increases its Gibbs free energy while not affecting the free energy of the transition state as drastically. The overall effect lowers the reaction's activation energy and facilitates the use of mild reaction temperatures (77 to 147 °C) and low catalyst loading.^{88,89} These mild conditions can also help partially preserve the β -O-4' linkages in lignin even enough degradation usually occurs to significantly affect lignin upgradeability.^{3,54} The resulting increase in the activity of destabilized protons reduces the activation energy of both proton-catalyzed hydrolysis and dehydration reactions, but has been shown to accelerate depolymerization reactions more, which helps to reduce degradation and humin formation.^{84,86,90,91}

Therefore, solvent use offers an option to mitigate, if not overcome, the effects caused by the rapid degradation of lignin and polysaccharides. Lignin still suffers from significant degradation and cellulose was still challenging to depolymerize in simple reaction systems. In fact, reasonable yields were only attained in the previously discussed flow-through reaction setups. This type of setup led to similar trade-offs between yields and concentration as were reported for pure water systems (with glucose yields between 66 and 69% at concentrations between 2 and 1.7 wt%).⁸⁴ However, the solvent could be fairly easily separated from water using additives like liquid CO₂ or apolar solvents like benzene or toluene to leave behind a concentrated (up to 13 wt%) aqueous sugar solution.^{84,85,92} The main challenge for this remains the cost of solvent recovery, recycling and make-up as well as risks associated with its stability and

flamability.^{93,94} Nevertheless, techno-economic analyses have shown this approach could be economically competitive for the production of the second generation of ethanol, furfural, and pulp compared to state-of-the-art technologies.^{78,95}

When alcohols are used as organic co-solvents in the depolymerization of polysaccharides, they incorporate in the anomeric position of C₅ and C₆ carbohydrates. The main pathway is acid-catalyzed hydrolysis followed by Fisher glycosylation or transglycosylation reactions, which both yield α - and β -alkyl mono glycosides (5 and 6).^{46,59,96} Such monoglycosides are commonly formed in catalytic biomass fractionation under acidic conditions if the pulping media is high in alcohol content and can be produced at yields that reach 47%.^{46,59,97} Independently, alcoholysis (alcohol content $\geq 95\%$) in combination with Lewis or Brønsted acid catalysis is widely applied in holocellulose and cellulose depolymerization. These solvents systems significantly lower the apparent activation energy of the depolymerization reaction from around 27–43 kcal·mol⁻¹ in water to 13 kcal·mol⁻¹ in ethanol mixtures.⁹⁸ For instance, alcoholysis of cellulose in methanol produced a 57% yield of methyl glucosides at an 85% cellulose conversion while hydrolysis of cellulose in water under the same reaction conditions (polyoxometalate catalyst, 147 °C)⁹⁹ resulted in a cellulose conversion of only 20% and a glucose yield of 7.1%.

[H3] Cellulose depolymerization in concentrated acid and ionic liquids

An alternative to using very high temperatures and short residence times is to unravel cellulose crystallinity, which drastically increases the accessibility of glycosidic bonds and leads cellulose to behave similarly to hemicellulose and be easily hydrolyzable. Concentrated mineral acids are known for their potential to swell and decrystallize cellulose.^{100–102} The large amount of unsolvated proton ions in concentrated acids can disrupt the hydrogen bonds in the crystalline structure of cellulose by forming strong hydrogen linkages with cellulose hydroxyl groups.^{61,103,104} As a result, cellulose is completely dissolved leading to an amorphous structure, which hydrolyzes much faster and can be converted at high yields to glucose, which was first reported in the early 1800s by Braconnot.^{105,106} More recently, ionic liquids (ILs) have been shown

to similarly completely dissolve cellulose by breaking hydrogen bonds between cellulose strands by forming stronger interactions between the cellulose and their ionic species. In addition, the activation energy of cellulose hydrolysis can also be decreased by the presence of ILs.^{107–109} The strongly ionic environment of ILs has been proposed to stabilize the positive charge of oxocarbenium ions, which lowers the Gibbs free energy of the transition state (E_a of 22 kcal·mol⁻¹ in [Emim][Cl] and methanesulfonic acid)¹¹⁰ and enables the saccharification of cellulose at temperatures where no reaction would have occurred in pure water.¹⁰⁷ However, this hydrolysis requires a careful balance of the water content in solution in order to facilitate hydrolysis without leading to the precipitation of the cellulose and reformation of hydrogen bonds. Typically, after dissolution, the hydrolysis process is performed by slowly adding water in the presence of acid in order to cleave the glycosidic bonds without precipitating the cellulose.¹⁰⁸

With both the use of concentrated acids and ILs, processes feature high reaction rate and low operational temperature and pressure.^{61,111,112} However, they face high operational and capital cost due to the need for acid IL recovery and corrosion resistant materials. A few commercial processes have been developed based on concentrated acids, notably using HCl, which can be recovered thanks to its volatility.^{113,114} The higher cost of ILs and their recovery has, as of yet, made this technology prohibitively expensive, but many efforts are still focused on lowering their production and recovery costs.^{115–117}

[H3] Enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose

The enzymatic hydrolysis of hemicellulose and cellulose involves the acid catalyzed cleavage of these polysaccharides to soluble sugars by amino acid residues in cellulases' or xylanases' active sites.¹¹⁸ Due to their high selectivity and activity, the enzymatic processes occur **under** mild conditions (usually around 50 °C) and **do not** produce any degradation product despite leveraging similar chemistry to what occurs with traditional acid catalyzed hydrolysis. The enzyme's catalytic site reduces the activation energy for hydrolysis (to as low as 1.2 kcal·mol⁻¹ for cellulose) while not affecting the activation energy of glucose degradation.^{119,120} Unfortunately, a similarly simple enzymatic process for lignin depolymerization (**but not**

necessarily a hydrolytic process) has yet to be discovered/developed. The hydrolysis kinetics for polysaccharides are largely governed by the extent of exposure of glycosidic bonds in the substrate, which can be measured as the accessible surface area to enzymes.¹²¹ For this reason, a pretreatment process is almost always required to remove lignin and hemicellulose, expose more cellulose surface and decrease crystallinity.^{28,85,122} The lack of degradation products and the mild conditions that result from enzyme use have made this the preferred industrial process in current biorefineries. However, the need for a two-step process, slow kinetics, and the cost of enzyme production continues to fuel interest in purely chemical alternatives.

[H1] Stabilization of intermediates

Each of the approaches discussed above influences the polysaccharide depolymerization kinetics by various factors that affects the kinetics of glycosidic bond cleavage but almost always lead to lignin degradation. An alternate approach to modifying unfavorable depolymerization and degradation kinetics, is to introduce a stabilization reaction that reacts with and *traps* reactive intermediates, which is more favorable than the degradation reactions. As we will discuss, this strategy can lead to the simultaneous valorization of both polysaccharides and lignin.

[H2] Reductive fractionation: *lignin first*

Currently, the dominant lignin valorization strategy, known as reductive catalytic fractionation (RCF), catalytic upstream biorefining, or lignin-first, involves the stabilization of lignin reactive fragments - extracted from lignocellulose by solvolysis - by catalytic hydrogenation and hydrogenolysis during the biomass fractionation process usually in the presence of a heterogeneous metal redox catalyst (e.g., Pd/C, Ni/C, RANEY® Ni).^{3,19,123,124} These reactions can be performed in the presence of molecular hydrogen, or under transfer hydrogenation conditions using an external hydrogen donor (e.g. MeOH, iPrOH) or internal hydrogen donors released from biomass (e.g. formic acid, reducing carbohydrates).^{3,19,123,124}

The solvolysis pathway depends on the nature of the pulping media such as solvent properties (protic, aprotic, polar, etc.), nature of the acid if present (strong, weak, Lewis or Brønsted) and overall acidity.^{46,125-127} In protic solvents, under pH-neutral or low acidity conditions, solvolysis predominantly leads to the formation of unsaturated lignin monomers (**18/19** to **20**).^{59,128-132} At higher acidity, the same systems tend to yield acidolysis products (**18/19** to **24** and Hibbert ketones), and the selectivity towards acidolysis products can be increased by switching from protic to aprotic polar or nonpolar solvents.^{40,127} Products from both homolysis and acidolysis reactions are prone to condensation, but can be rapidly stabilized by catalytic hydrogenation of unsaturated bonds. At high concentration of the protic solvent, a competing incorporation

of the solvent into the alpha position of the β -O-4' moieties were observed (18/19 to 22), which could inhibit cleavage pathways, but assist lignin solubilization.^{133,134}

Any lignin fragments that are liberated by solvolysis but remain oligomeric can have their linkages further cleaved on the catalytic sites, provided these fragments are small enough to reach the surface of the catalyst. The β -O-4' moiety can undergo various transformations depending on the nature of the metal catalyst and hydrogen availability.¹³⁵ At low hydrogen pressures (e.g. around 1 bar or neutral atmosphere), the β -O-4' moiety can undergo hydrogen neutral C—O bond cleavage via the corresponding ketone intermediate (21).¹³⁶ However, direct hydrogenolysis will be preferred if excess of hydrogen is available.

There is a plethora of proposed mechanisms based on model compounds and the particular pathway depends on the conditions and, importantly, on the nature of the catalytic sites.¹³⁵ In general, the ease of hydrogenolysis of lignin linkages follows the order of bond strengths: α -O-4' < β -O-4' < 4-O-5' \ll C—C.^{36,137,138} Therefore, the most enthalpy-favorable are α -O-4' and β -O-4' bonds hydrogenolysis. Recent work has also used RCF to elucidate mechanisms of lignin biosynthesis, suggesting, based on measurements of monomers being released, that monomer transport during this biosynthesis may control C—C and C—O linkage formation.¹³⁹

Due to high complexity of the process and wide variety of conditions both solvolysis or hydrogenolysis of the resulting lignin fragments could be the rate determining step. Beckham, Román-Leshkov and co-workers demonstrated that under RCF conditions (H_2 , Ni/C, MeOH), the apparent activation barriers for the hydrogenolysis and the acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of lignin β -O-4' model compounds (arylglycerol- β -aryl ethers) were very similar (40 kcal·mol⁻¹ vs 36 kcal·mol⁻¹), which was much higher than the activation energy for lignin extraction (~15 kcal·mol⁻¹).^{140,141} However, for the same model compounds under different conditions (H_2 , dioxane-water, Pd/C) Dumesic, Ralph, and coworkers found that apparent E_a of the

hydrogenolysis step was nearly twice as low ($19 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) and closer to what was observed for lignin extraction.¹⁴²

Even though the hydrogenolysis reactions can be slow, the hydrogenation and hydrogenolysis of reactive intermediates proceeds much more favorably than condensation as evidenced by the fact that condensation mechanisms are almost fully curtailed. Indeed, reductive catalytic fractionation produces monomers at yields that are close to theoretical maximum of 50% (Figure 3b).

As for the carbohydrate fractions, cellulose can be almost fully recovered as a solid (up to 97%), while the retention of hemicellulose in the solid pulp varies substantially with conditions (5–95%).^{46,143–145} In most cases, hemicellulose can be valorized as alkyl glycosides (**5 and 6**), polyols (**10 and 11**), etc. leading to reasonable carbon balances for these processes.^{29,126} However, these fractionation methods are **limited by technical difficulties such as catalyst and solvent recovery, catalyst deactivation, mass transfer limitations, pulp contamination and high energy demand.** These issues, **which are not yet well understood, are all linked to high operational and capital cost, which** have so far limited scale-up and thus, **delayed the potential commercialization of this approach.**

[H2] Lignin oxidation

Oxidation of the secondary hydroxyl group at the $C\alpha$ position in $\beta\text{—O—}4'$ motifs can also act as a stabilization approach since the oxidized functionality precludes dehydration and thus the formation of a benzylic carbocation. This strategy has been an attractive route to activate $\beta\text{—O—}4'$ linkages to enable new cleavage mechanisms.^{146,147} Specifically, oxidation of the benzylic hydroxyl group ($\alpha\text{—OH}$, see Figure **2, 16 to 21**) leads to a reduction in BDE of the $C\beta\text{—O}$ ether bond from $68.2\text{--}71.8 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to $55.9\text{--}57.1 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, where oxidation of the primary alcohol ($\gamma\text{—OH}$) decreases the $C\beta\text{—O}$ ether bond BDE to $56.7\text{--}59.1 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$.¹⁴⁶ In addition, both of these transformations will activate the $C\beta\text{—H}$ bond making its proton more labile¹⁴⁸ and thereby promote other depolymerization routes (e.g., retro-aldol reaction¹⁴⁹,

deformylation¹⁵⁰). Importantly, the acid-catalyzed cleavage of lignin oxidized at the α -OH position (Figure 2, 21) enables the abstraction of the proton in the C β position leading to the formation of a diketone product (27).¹⁵¹ The formic acid-catalyzed cleavage of an oxidized model lignin dimer was calculated to have an activation energy of 21 kcal·mol⁻¹, which is comparable to carbohydrates hydrolysis reactions.¹⁵²

Selective oxidation of the α -OH group in the β -O-4' motif has been widely studied and systems based on DDQ^{56,146,153} or TEMPO¹⁵⁴ analogs, NHPI,¹⁵⁵ oxovanadium complexes, and metalloporphyrins, etc.¹⁴⁷ have been reported. Furthermore, the more challenging selective oxidation of the γ -OH group has also been accomplished using Cu/TEMPO, TEMPO, or iridium complexes.^{150,156,157} The subsequent cleavage or depolymerization step can take place by hydrolysis or by oxidative (e.g., Baeyer-Villiger)¹⁴⁷, reductive (e.g., photocatalyzed, Zn/NH₄Cl)¹⁵⁸⁻¹⁶⁰, or redox-neutral reactions (photocatalyzed,¹⁵⁵ retro-aldol,¹⁵⁶ NH₂OH¹⁶¹ or HCOOH/HCOONa mediated systems^{151,152}). Due to the weakening of the β -O-4' ether bond, the cleavage reaction can be performed at milder conditions, which has resulted in high yields, especially in model studies (67% for α -OH motifs and 100% for their oxidized equivalents).^{162,163}

The main obstacle of the oxidative strategy is that it is incompatible with the lignocellulose fractionation and, thus, requires lignin to be extracted prior to oxidation. Therefore, all the methods, tested on structurally modified lignins obtained by conventional fractionation, led to either low yields of monomers or poor product selectivity.^{56,163,164} High yields (52 wt%) of oxygenated monomer mixtures were notably achieved with enzymatically extracted lignin, due to its near native structure.¹⁵¹ However, enzymatically extracted lignin, which requires several **conventional** ball milling and enzymatic treatments is not considered an industrially relevant approach.

Oxidation strategies could play an essential role in producing high value compounds from lignin since they provide access to functionalized phenol derivatives that are not available through other depolymerization strategies. Therefore, further developments should address either their integration into pretreatment or by

combining the oxidation methods with another stabilizing approach to preserve the lignin during extraction as detailed below.

[H2] High alcohol organosolv

Alcohols have been used in biomass fractionation for close to a century but certain benefits of their use for lignin extraction have only been understood recently.¹⁶⁵ During extraction, lignin undergoes dehydration of its β -O-4' motif proceeding through formation of benzylic carbocation (Figure 2, 18), which can be intercepted by alcohols as nucleophiles to form ethers (22). Therefore, in solvent mixtures containing predominantly alcohols (>95%) etherification of the alpha position takes place, which minimizes condensation reactions and slows down β -O-4' bond cleavage.^{133,166-169} Interestingly, the BDE of α C-OMe bond is significantly lower (70 kcal·mol⁻¹) than the corresponding α C-OH BDE 89 kcal·mol⁻¹.¹⁷⁰ Nevertheless, other factors such as Le Chatelier's principle and lignin's hydrophobicity could be the driving force for the more effective carbocation stabilization in alcohols compared to aqueous media. Both model studies and butanosolv biomass fractionation demonstrated that the ether-stabilized benzylic position is less prone to degradation. Preservation of the (etherified) β -O-4' motifs was demonstrated by NMR analysis, where the amount of non-degraded β -aryl ether bonds increased from 3-17% for lignin isolated using conventional method (kraft, soda, etc.) to 63% and 51% in the case of ethano- and butanosolv isolation, respectively.^{166,171} Lignins stabilized in such a way could be selectively depolymerized to monomers at yields up to 35% (for 18% of the lignin extracted), which is 15-20% of theoretical yields based on the original lignin but four times higher than what was obtained with technical lignin from the same biomass species.^{49,166-168}

Lignins stabilized by etherification at the alpha position are valuable substrates for further modification. The reversible nature of alpha-etherification can be used to regenerate native-like lignin, notably, by treatment under mild acidic dioxanosolv conditions (0.1 M HCl, 100 °C; albeit with some degradation as evidenced by a 30% decrease in β -O-4' ether linkages content). Interestingly, these α -alkylated β -O-

4' motifs can also serve as protecting agents to promote the selective oxidation of the γ -OH group and thereby enable alternative defunctionalization pathways.^{97,150}

Similar to organosolv processing, the fractionation with aliphatic alcohols preserves most of the carbohydrate fraction. The solid residue obtained from butanosolv beech wood fractionation (catalyzed by HCl) was subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis, and resulted in reducing sugars yields of **ca.** 70 wt% (based on the original carbohydrate content in biomass).¹⁶⁶ Part of the more labile hemicellulose reacts with the solvent during the fractionation process to form the corresponding alkyl glycosides in detectable quantities.

[H2] Functionalization with acetals

Another even more common form of reversible functionalization chemistry is acetal formation, which involves preferentially a diol reacting with a carbonyl compound to form a cyclic acetal or ketal while liberating water. The reaction with an aldehyde is particularly favorable and thus could be an interesting candidate for preventing degradation reactions, as any diol or aldehyde trapped in an acetal ring cannot dehydrate or condense. Lignin's β -O-4' linkage (**16**) has a diol structure as do many polysaccharide functionalities (**3 and 4**). In addition, one of lignin's degradation mechanism occurs via the production of reactive aldehydes. All of these functionalities are potential stabilization targets by forming acetals (Figure **3a**). We will first review the studies that have focused on lignin functionalization and then discuss functionalization of polysaccharides.

[H3] Lignin

As discussed above, the phenyl-ether bonds, particularly those in the β -O-4' motifs readily undergo modifications leading to degradation notably via the formation of a benzylic carbocation and subsequent condensation reactions (Figure **2, 18 to 28**). A potential solution to prevent these undesired processes, is to stabilize the substrate prior to carbocation formation. Specifically, β -O-4' linkage's 1,3-propanediol moiety (Figure **2, 16**) can be made to react very favorably with aldehydes, including formaldehyde and

most linear aldehyde such as acetaldehyde or propionaldehyde (29–31), to form cyclic 1,3-dioxane structures (17).³⁴ Trapping the β —O—4''s hydroxyl groups in the form of a cyclic acetal prevents their dehydration and subsequent degradation reactions. Though acetal formation is a reversible reaction, the acetal form can be highly favored at low water conditions (<20 wt%) due to Le Chatelier's principle and the formation of water that accompanies the reaction. Furthermore, computational studies with model lignin dimers have shown acetal formation to be far more favorable than condensation reactions, with an activation barrier that was calculated as 7.6 to 4.8 kcal·mol⁻¹ lower depending on whether formaldehyde or propionaldehyde, respectively, was used for the functionalization reaction.¹⁷²

As a result, aldehyde-stabilized lignin was shown by 2D ¹H–¹³C heteronuclear single quantum coherence NMR to have almost all its original native β —O—4' linkages trapped in the form of a cyclic acetal.^{34,44} The extracted lignin could then be further upgraded; either directly in the pretreatment liquor or isolated from the other biomass components. In particular, this aldehyde-stabilized lignin, which is soluble in polar solvents such as ethers and alcohols could then be depolymerized by hydrogenolysis over various heterogeneous metal catalysts including Pd, Ru or Ni at yields ranging from 42 to 50% of the original lignin for a typical wild type hardwood (Figure 3c).^{34,44,51} Even with isolation, overall monomer yields were often comparable (within 5%) of the yields obtained by reductive catalytic fractionation techniques. These yields are considered to be near theoretical quantities of monomers attainable via ether cleavage.

Aldehyde protection could also be combined with the oxidative depolymerization approach.⁵⁶ Specifically, lignin functionalized with propionaldehyde could be deprotected and subsequently oxidized (α -OH) in a single step using a 2,3-dichloro-5,6-dicyano-1,4-benzoquinone (DDQ) and nitric acid catalytic under an oxygen atmosphere. A HCOOH/HCOONa mediated cleavage of the oxidized lignin's β —O—4' ether bonds resulted in a 31–36 mol% (depending on whether a catalytic or stoichiometric quantity of the catalyst was used) yield of monophenolic compounds with a selectivity over 90% to diketone products.⁵⁶ The

resulting yield was still lower by 10–20% than reported for the same protected lignin that was depolymerized with hydrogenolysis.⁴⁴

Acetals can also be formed further along in lignin extraction to stabilize monomeric depolymerization products. During the fractionation of lignocellulosic biomass in acidic conditions the aforementioned benzylic carbocation is formed and can condense.¹⁶⁷ However the resulting intermediates (**18 and 19**) can also undergo either proton abstraction (C3-pathway) or loss of formaldehyde through β — γ bond cleavage (C2-pathway, **24**). The C2-pathway will yield a single type of aldehyde (**24**), where the C3-pathway will result in a group of products known as Hibbert ketones. Monomeric products from model acidic hydrolysis studies were almost exclusively derived from C3-pathway, which indicated that the aldehydes rapidly condensed under these conditions.

Whereas above we described how the diol functionalities in the lignin backbone could be functionalized with external aldehydes, in this case these monomeric C2-aldehydes formed upon acid catalyzed lignin depolymerization can be trapped with external diols (**33–39**), once again forming stable acetals (**25**). When simple β —O—4' model compounds were subjected to acidolysis in 1,4-dioxane at 140 °C using TfOH in the presence of ethylene glycol, protected aldehydes (**25**) were observed in up to quantitative yields (in the case of arylethanol- β -aryl ethers model compounds).¹⁷³ Beside ethylene glycol (**33**), other, potentially bio-derived 1,3-propanediol, 1,2-butanediol, and glycerol could also be used forming the corresponding 1,3-dioxolanes or 1,3-dioxanes respectively. Notably, when glycerol was used, regioisomers (both 1,3-dioxolane and 1,3-dioxane) and several diastereomers were formed. The use of more complex arylglycerol- β -aryl ether models resulted in 55% lower C2-acetals yields due to the competing C3-pathway and condensation of the carbocation intermediate (**18 to 28**).¹⁶⁷ Hibbert ketones formed through the C3-pathway could also undergo protection forming the corresponding ketals. Interestingly, when more complex models were used, the formaldehyde released via the C2-pathway (**23**) was trapped by ethylene glycol to form 1,3-dioxolane (**32** in up to 85% yield) and could also be quantified.¹⁶⁸ This ethylene glycol stabilization method

was further tested using various metal triflates instead of triflic acid, on 28 lignins from different biomass sources and obtained by different isolation techniques. The yield of the targeted C2-acetals was proportional to the quantity of β -O-4' linkages in the starting lignin and was as high as 8.4 wt% based on the original Klason lignin in biomass (Figure 3d).⁴⁹ The fate of more complex lignin models comprising a combination of β -O-4', β -5' and β - β' linkages were studied and acetal formation was observed in the case of models containing β -O-4' and β -5' motifs, where model containing β - β' linkage undergoes acid catalyzed epimerization.

Acid catalyzed fractionation of cedar woodmeal was demonstrated by Watanabe and coworkers who detected up to 4.8 wt% (based on Klason lignin) stable monomeric C2-dimethyl-acetals in toluene/methanol mixtures.¹⁷⁴ Recently, the acid catalyzed fractionation of pine lignocellulose in the presence of ethylene glycol resulted in the production of C2-acetals at a yield of 8.8 wt% (based on Klason lignin, Figure 3e).¹²⁷ The remaining cellulose-rich solids were enzymatically digestible (up to 85% yield), while part of the cellulose and hemicellulose were dissolved during processing, forming stable alkyl glycosides. After hydrolysis of alkyl glycosides, the total overall glucose yield reached 77 wt% and the yield of hemicellulose sugars was around 30 wt% based on the weight of the original cellulose and hemicellulose.

[H3] Polysaccharides

As was previously discussed, there are many ways to avoid carbohydrate degradation to humins without stabilization. However, in recent years, carbohydrate stabilization techniques have emerged in parallel to their associated techniques developed for lignin. The hydroxyl groups in carbohydrates can also function as 1,2- and 1,3-diols, and thus act as targets for acetal functionalization with aldehyde. Carbohydrates are known to react with both aldehydes and ketones in a presence of an acid-catalysts to produce acetals (Figure 1b, 3 to 7 and 4 to 8 and 9) and ketals and water.^{175,176} Given that these reactions are generally reversible, the functionalization is favored in a solvent-rich environment (e.g. <20wt% water) like those found in organosolv processes by Le Chatelier's principle. However, aprotic solvents are preferred as hydroxyl

groups in the solvent can competitively react with aldehydes, limiting functionalization. Conversely, the removal of the acetal and recovery of simple sugars is easily carried out in aqueous environment with an acid catalyst.^{21,34,44,177}

The formation of the acetal thought to occur through a hemiacetal intermediate followed by the formation of oxocarbenium ions.^{177–179} The latter being the rate limiting step. Nevertheless, the rate of sugar functionalization appears to be significantly faster compared to dehydration reactions, which limits degradation.²¹ A similar acetal (**32**) formation reaction between glycerol and formaldehyde had an apparent activation energy of 14 kcal·mol⁻¹,¹⁸⁰ which is notably lower than what it has been observed for sugar dehydration (Figure 1 **a** and **b**). The use of acetal functionalization to trap intermediates has been used in the depolymerization of both polysaccharides, hemicellulose, and cellulose. However, given that cellulose requires high temperatures (>180 °C) in acid organosolv processes, the rate of degradation of functionalized sugars, which occurs via the equilibrium with unprotected sugars is not insignificant and can lower yields.²¹

Recently, we reported that when an aldehyde is added to an acid organosolv pretreatment (using an aprotic co-solvent), hemicellulose-derived sugars and lignin react with the aldehyde producing acetal-stabilized xylose (**7**) and stabilized-lignin fragments (**17**) near theoretical yields.^{21,34,44} In the case of cellulose, the addition of an aldehyde to the previously discussed flow-through setup used with a GVL solvent produced acetal-stabilized glucose (in the form of two isomers, **8** and **9**) that, due to reduced degradation, increased glucose recovery and concentration of 2 to 3-fold. This increase allowed us to reach product yields around 70% and equivalent glucose concentrations close to 5 wt%. Degradation was reduced because these modified carbohydrates cannot undergo dehydration, thus, eliminating the primary pathway to humin formation. Depending on the aldehyde, the formation of this acetal can result in a new stereogenic center and generate two isomers.⁵¹ However, this stereogenic center is lost upon deprotection.

The stabilization of biomass-derived carbohydrates had also been reported by forming ketal groups.^{21,34,44,181–183} Ketalization of biomass-derived carbohydrates has been accomplished in an acetone-based acid organosolv pretreatment containing 70–90% acetone and dilute mineral acids.¹⁸² Similar to aldehydes, acetone reacted with carbohydrates producing ketal sugars, which helped avoid the dehydration of sugars.^{182,183} This method has been used to improve the quality of bio-oil by protecting carbohydrates from degradation forming C₅ and C₆ ketals¹⁸¹ and more recently, in acid organosolv biomass pretreatment (along with other protecting groups) but this led to similar carbohydrate yields to those in control experiments⁴⁴. The absence of significant increase in carbohydrate yields could be attributed to the similar rates between protection reactions and degradation reactions, which likely limited the effect of stabilization.

These resulting functionalized sugars can prevent degradation and then be converted back to simple sugars but could also be explored as intermediates for further reactions. They can be produced at very high yields from biomass polysaccharides in a single step and thus could be interesting platform molecules. Recent work has shown that they have unique reactivity and separation properties and, thus could open new upgrading schemes within biorefineries. This is the case of diformylxylose, formaldehyde-stabilized xylose (**7**), which can be converted to furfural (**12**) through a unique reaction mechanism that is independent of Lewis acid addition and favours furfural production with only Brønsted acid addition at 160 °C.²¹ Additionally, given the volatility of diformylxylose, it can be purified by distillation and upgraded into xylitol (**10**) eliminating one of the most expensive and complex steps in the production of xylitol, which is xylitol purification by chromatography.¹⁸⁴

[H1] Stabilization approaches: comparison, sustainability and future directions

The development of economically successful biorefineries will require the development of easily implementable catalytic methods that can sustainably depolymerize all major biopolymers. A key factor for economics and sustainability is to isolate high yields of individual molecules, while avoiding significant loss in atoms, especially carbon, given the energy intensive process involved in fixing atmospheric carbon

by plants. Achieving higher yields reduce the process cost and environmental impact of the resulting products. A lower environmental impact can also only be achieved by implementing “green” processing steps. For this reason, we will first briefly compare selected stabilization methods, which include RCF (Figure 3b), stabilization with reactive aldehydes (3c), stabilization with alcohols (3d) in high alcohol content medium, as well as stabilization with diols in aprotic media (3e) notably by taking into account the main principles of green chemistry.¹⁸⁵ We will then discuss the sustainable upgrading and use of the monomers produced by these stabilization methods.

[H2] Comparison of selected stabilization approaches

RCF and aldehyde stabilization can lead to near-theoretical yield of monomers from lignin (Figure 3 b – c), while stabilization or alcohols (Figure 3d) usually results in lower yield of monophenolic compounds based on the original Klason lignin content due to side reactions originating from incomplete intermediate trapping and low efficiency of lignin extraction. However, in RCF, some of the carbohydrate fraction is converted to polyols (Figure 1 and 4b, 10 and 11) which may be desirable but limits upgrading possibilities. When reactive aldehydes are used for stabilization, their incorporation into sugars, lignin or lignin monomers can be desirable or create complications depending on the desired application.

When comparing the reagents used for stabilization, RCF uses H₂ which is typically less expensive than the aldehydes or alcohols that are used (summarized in Figure 3a), and is essentially integrated into the final product, which is attractive in terms of atom economy. The acetal as well as the alcohol functionalization approaches (Figure 3 c – e) in principle use carbonyl compounds as protective groups to preserve the β—O—4' moiety. Because derivatization is not ideal from a sustainability perspective (8th principle of green chemistry),¹⁸⁵ either deprotection needs to be extremely efficient, which is usually easier for alcohol stabilization due to the lower stability of this functionality, or the functionalized intermediate can directly become a useful products, removing the need to cycle the stabilization agent. In any case, these stabilization

agents (H₂, H-donors, carbonyl compounds, alcohols) should be produced from renewable resources, which is systematically possible but not necessarily industrially available.

A very important issue in terms of sustainability and green chemistry (5th principle)¹⁸⁵ for any process is the nature, recyclability, and amount of required solvent used. In this regard, several stabilization strategies offer possibilities for the use of bio-derived and non-toxic reaction media. The process solvent demand can be represented by the biomass-to-liquor ratio, where stabilization strategies are close to current conventional fractionation processes (from 1:10 to 1:20 versus 1:3 to 1:10 depending on the biomass origin). RCF predominantly utilize alcohol/water solutions (from 50 to 100% MeOH, EtOH or BuOH). Like RCF, the high alcohol fractionation process relies on bio-derivable alcohols. Stabilization with diols can be performed using renewable non-toxic dimethyl carbonate.¹⁸⁶ Acetal functionalization with aldehydes has been mostly performed with 1,4-dioxane, which is fossil-based and not a green solvent, but has also been performed with γ -valerolactone (GVL), which is green and relatively easy to produce from glucose.³⁴ The aldehydes that are used are currently largely fossil-based and would need to be produced from renewable feedstocks. All methods generally involve handling flammable organic solvents posing additional engineering requirements. The most demanding in this regard is RCF **when run with molecular hydrogen due the often-elevated operational pressure and required recycling of the gas**. Biomass loading and discharging of solid carbohydrate residues **must be compatible with a hydrogen atmosphere, which requires** specialized infrastructure associated with high capital costs.

To improve process sustainability, alternative solvents may also be designed which incorporate depolymerization and subsequent stabilization functions directly into their structure. This concept has been demonstrated on arylethanol- β -aryl ethers model compounds for the stabilization of reactive C2- aldehydes in a H⁺IL system in conjunction with ethylene glycol stabilization to obtain up to 60% yield of C2-acetals or alternatively in a Brønsted acid/RuNP@ IL system in order to obtain C2-alcohols (64% yield) by

acidolysis in conjunction with catalytic hydrogenation.¹⁸⁷ In this case, both the depolymerization, as well as the stabilization function has been incorporated into the reaction medium.

Regarding processes energy balance and efficiency, methods focused on lignin structure preservation using alcohols or aldehydes (Figure 3 d and c) are the mildest and can be conducted at 80 (5 h) and 90 °C (6 h) respectively, but at the cost of a long reaction time. Both RCF and stabilization with diols are significantly shorter (from 1 to 2 h) but demand harsher conditions around 200 °C and 140 °C, respectively. However, the latter two cases deliver monophenolic compounds directly, whereas the former two need an additional depolymerization step. On the other hand, aldehyde stabilization (Figure 3c) involves the isolation of the three biomass fractions, which allows for the subsequent use of a broader range of lignin and carbohydrate valorization methods as well as the independent optimization of the fractionation and valorization steps. These advantages have to be weighed against the need to cycle the stabilizing reagent, which will undoubtedly increase process complexity.

The alcohol or aldehyde stabilization methods are essentially compatible with already established organosolv pulping methods, and only require adjustment of solvents and/or reaction conditions. With RCF, near theoretical yields are obtained from the lignin fraction. Still, the C₅ sugars are often partially converted or lost at conditions of high delignification and catalyst recycling is a key challenge that remains unsolved at industrial scale. At the laboratory scale proposed solutions for catalyst recycling include physical separation of the catalyst in a different compartment,^{58,59,188} or catalyst cage and flowing newly solubilized lignin to the catalyst surface,¹⁸⁹ isolation of the magnetically active solid catalyst using a magnet¹⁸⁹ or integrating a second catalytic step that is able to fully convert all process residues to predominantly liquid products¹⁹⁰.

[H2] Renewable atom balance of platform chemicals obtained via stabilization strategies and strategies for potential applications

All of the stabilization methods covered here allow the recovery of several platform chemicals at high yield and selectivity (Figure 4). To reflect the extent of renewable atom retention in these components and the subsequent use of these components (Figure 4a), and for their quantitative comparison, Biomass Utilization Efficiency (BUEs, see glossary and calculation details in the SI)¹⁹¹ can be used, which is analogous to the classical definition of atom economy, emphasized by the 2nd principle of green chemistry. BUEs for the molecules resulting from stabilization methods clearly result in very high renewable atom retention (Figure 4 b and c).

The novel stabilization methods can deliver higher yields of well-known platform chemicals from the hemicellulose and cellulose fractions, for which several established conversion strategies exist (Figure 4b). For lignin, the novel stabilization/depolymerization methods have made available previously unforeseen aromatic monomers that are structurally more complex than the simple molecules usually generated under harsher processes such as pyrolysis or liquefaction.^{14,192} These molecules could facilitate further atom-economic transformations that are still only at the demonstration stage (Figure 4c). Very recently, great progress has been made regarding the synthesis of novel polymers starting from aromatics obtained by the aforementioned stabilization strategies (e.g. Figure 2, 21)^{35,44,124,167,174} Specifically, propyl guaiacol (42) can be a source of bisphenols either by demethylation of the methoxy group (Figure 4c, 42 to 50) or by acid-catalyzed condensation with formaldehyde (Figure 4c, 42 to 51). These have been used for the manufacture of bio-based polyesters,^{193–195} polycarbonates,^{193–195} polycyanurates,^{193–195} as well as epoxy nanocomposites¹⁹⁶. Furthermore, propanol guaiacol (21) and a depolymerization mixture obtained by RCF, which was rich in lignin oligomers (like 52), were glycolated. The resulting epoxy resins could substitute up to 75% of bisphenol A diglycidyl ether in several formulations.¹⁹⁷ Isoeugenol (43) obtained by RCF was also used in epoxy resin synthesis by transformation into diglycidyl ether in two steps: glycidylation, followed by the epoxidation of the double bond.¹⁹⁸ Products of the C2-acetal stabilization could also be used to prepare bisphenols through transacetalization (Figure 4c, 25 to 53) and subsequent glycidylation reactions, as demonstrated by Watanabe et al. using the protected C2-acetal as aromatic monomer obtained

from lignocellulose.¹⁹⁹ In all cases the mechanical and thermal properties of the bio-based polymers compared favorably or were superior than conventional materials.¹⁹⁵

The lignin-based emerging bisphenols have high BUEs values (83–92%) and serve as sustainable replacement of BPA. As comparison, producing phenol (starting material for the synthesis of bisphenol-A) from lignin would lead to more than a 50% loss of the native monomer structure (BUEs = 47%, Figure 4c). The high BUEs numbers of these mono-aromatics demonstrate that it is preferable to find strategies to incorporate these monomers into novel products with little structural modification. This approach holds enormous potential in terms of green chemistry, as it allows the manufacture of novel sustainable products with potentially superior biodegradability and lower toxicity. Lower toxicity was already demonstrated for some of the new polymer building blocks in the case of BPA analogs, where the best examples demonstrate no detectable estrogenic activity.^{193,200}

The higher oxygen content of the lignin-derived monophenolic compounds offers great opportunities for the design of waste-free coupling pathways,^{190,201} e.g. for insertion of heteroatoms via the borrowing hydrogen strategy or by activation of aromatic —OH and —OCH₃ groups.^{202–204} Such transformations could lead to markedly reducing waste for the production of fine chemicals, pharmaceutical intermediates and could open the way for the design of novel biologically active compounds (Figure 4c) (see SI, Scheme SI 4 for detailed synthesis strategies). Nitrogen incorporation is especially important for the creation of bioactive compounds like the formation of aniline from the phenol functionality on these structures, which has been demonstrated for propyl guaiacol (42) and ethyl guaiacol (obtained by RCF) via oxidation to the corresponding benzoquinone ketal and a subsequent reaction with glycine methyl ester hydrochloride. In the case of ethyl- or propyl guaiacol, this strategy leads to building blocks that can be converted to valuable carbazoles in a single step (47) (see SI, Scheme SI 4). Alternatively, aniline derivatives were obtained from ethyl guaiacol by Ni-catalyzed Buchwald-Hartwig amination via the corresponding pseudohalogenides. The atom economy of these transformations strongly depends on the nature of the pseudohalogenide that is

used. Therefore, the development of catalytic strategies for the direct activation of aromatic —OH and —OCH₃ groups either for BH amination or various cross-coupling reactions is an interesting future research direction.^{202–204} Another interesting study used propyl-guaiacol as the core building block to synthesize anticancer drug Gefitinib (Figure 4c, 42 to 45).²⁰⁵ Introduction of nitrogen was carried out via a Beckmann rearrangement resulting in dialkoxyanilines that were further converted to the desired drug molecule.

Another elegant method to introduce nitrogen into lignin derived monophenols (21) was the Ru-catalyzed amination of the primary alcohol moiety contained in dihydroconiferyl and dihydrosynapyl alcohol via the hydrogen borrowing approach. Seven membered N-heterocycles (49) were constructed from the resulting secondary amines, via the Pictet-Spengler reaction, with only water as a byproduct.²⁰¹ The modular synthesis strategy allowed obtaining a library of linear and cyclic amines which were tested for anti-microbial and anti-cancer properties with promising results.

Of course, lignin-derived monophenolics could also be subjected to defunctionalization reactions to produce direct drop-in substitutes for petrochemicals, which is still the most attractive alternative for current industries. The disadvantage of these approaches is reflected by the significantly reduced BUE numbers and the fact that available re-functionalization reactions are frequently highly polluting. Moreover, these challenging transformations usually require the cleavage of strong C—O and C—C bonds and, therefore, a higher energy input.

To illustrate the trade-offs between defunctionalizing bio-based molecules and producing direct drop-in substitutes for fossil-based molecules, the various production routes can be visualized using a modified three-dimensional van Krevelen plot (Figure 5). The tortuosity of a specific route through this space represents the change in functionality and of the original carbon skeleton, and, as a result, the overall efficiency of the transformation.²⁰⁶ Therefore, transformations with the fewest steps that minimize reactant alteration will show less tortuosity and a shorter distance.

An illustrative example is the synthesis of dicarboxylic acids and their methyl esters that are used in the preparation of polyesters: fossil based dimethyl terephthalate (DMT, **67**) from terephthalic acid (PTA, **66**) for PET production or its renewable analogues (Figure 5). Fossil-based DMT is obtained from terephthalic acid originating from oxidation of *p*-xylene (**57**). However, while *p*-xylene is a basic petrochemical building block, producing it from glucose^{206,207} requires 3 steps, and 2 additional steps will be needed to transform *p*-xylene to DMT (synthetic route A, Scheme SI 5). This requires a total of 2.4 tons of glucose for each ton of biomass incorporated into DMT. An alternative 4 step synthesis route to access DMT started from lignin,²⁰⁸ where lignin monophenols produced by RCF were converted into 4-alkylbenzoic acids (**70**) through selective demethoxylation followed by carbonylation. Subsequent oxidation yielded terephthalic acid (PTA) which was esterified to DMT (synthetic route C, Scheme SI 5). This route demands 1.8–2.3 of monomer (depending on its structure, see Scheme SI 3 in the SI) to produce 1 ton of final product. Another, recently commercialized strategy is targeting an alternative polymer structure that is based on 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid (FDCA, **61**). Once FDCA is co-polymerized with ethylene glycol, the properties of the obtained polymer are comparable and in some respect better than that of conventional PET.²⁰⁹ Among the presented alternatives, synthetic routes that include a direct (i.e. drop-in) substitution of DMT show a higher tortuosity (by about 1 unit) and greater length (0.25 and 3.0 respectively),²⁰⁶ especially in comparison with the production of an alternative building block (dimethyl 2,5-furandicarboxylate – DMFC, 0.44 and 1.8). The same conclusion comes from calculating BUEs values for these various routes. The most atom economical approach among these options will be the same – production of DMFC for PEF synthesis (**4 to 68**), which will result in preserving the most biomass derived atoms and therefore lower the demand for the starting material - 1.5 tons of glucose per ton of biomass incorporated into the monomer. This analysis illustrates that producing indirect replacements such as FDCA allow for the most efficient biomass utilization and the fewest processing steps, illustrating the importance of maximizing the biomass structures that are already available.

[H2] Opportunities and outlook

The stabilization chemistry reviewed here has brought new **opportunities** for biomass conversion, prior to which had been mostly governed by unfavorable depolymerization kinetics—i.e. where degradation reactions outpaced depolymerization reactions. Specifically, biomass conversion schemes were largely focused on creating favorable kinetics for polysaccharide conversion through the use of systems like concentrated acids, ionic liquids or enzymes. These traditional approaches usually ignored lignin, which was always the most difficult to depolymerize due to it having the most unfavorable kinetics. Stabilization strategies have allowed processes to be run under previously unfavorable kinetic conditions by trapping reactive intermediates and preventing undesirable degradation or repolymerization reactions. This has allowed the depolymerization of lignin in its more native form at high yields for the first time and simultaneously opened new routes for sugar production. These strategies can be used to produce lignin-derived monoaromatics along with carbohydrates or polyols that have largely retained all the atoms that were originally in the plant, which could facilitate conversion processes with high atom economy. Some of these lignin-derived mono-aromatics are even being made available for the first time by these processes, which has led to new valorization routes to various intermediates including bulk polymer precursors or high value pharmaceuticals. These resulting products can even have superior properties, including reduced toxicity compared to their fossil counterparts.

However, up to now, industry has largely favored direct drop-in replacements despite increased processing and lower atom economy notably due to the high initial cost of registering and regulating new products. At the same time, stabilization strategies systematically involve the use of an external functionalization agent to stabilize the reactive intermediates and a non-aqueous solvent, which both need to be produced and/or recycled throughout the process. This will inherently drive up costs and lower process sustainability but can be mitigated with emerging strategies including integrating the stabilization reagent into the desired product to improve the atom economy, or the use of alternative reaction media that incorporates the stabilization function and/or facilitates product separation.

Altogether, stabilization strategies have widened the panoply of attainable bio-based molecules while offering opportunities to drastically improve the atom economy of their production routes. **In addition to considering green chemistry principles, any scale-up will need to be economically viable and relatively easy to operate at scale in order to compete with conventional refineries.** Their industrial implementation will depend on similar progress occurring during the process development and engineering phases that lie ahead.

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[H1] Author contributions

JSL and KB designed the review. YM QS and MG wrote initial drafts of the document and prepared initial figures. All authors edited the manuscript.

[H1] Competing interests statement

The authors declare competing interests. J.S.L. is an inventor on European patent applications (EP16165180, EP19203000 and EP19202957) and has co-founded a spin-off company (Bloom Biorenewables) that seeks to produce lignin and sugars using methods described in this review.

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Display Items

Figure 1 | Depolymerization of polysaccharides in lignocellulosic biomass by the conventional acid hydrolysis. a) Acid hydrolysis of hemicellulose into xylose, dehydration of xylose into furfural and condensation of furfural into humins. b) Acid hydrolysis of cellulose into glucose, dehydration of glucose into 5-HMF and 5-HMF into humins. Ether, C—C, functionalization and hydrogen bonds are highlighted in blue, orange, red and pink, respectively. [a] Based on a hemicellulose hydrolysis review with Brønsted acids from Shi⁴¹. [b] Based on a xylose dehydration report with Brønsted acids from Choudhary et al.²¹⁰ [c] Based on a cellulose hydrolysis review with Brønsted acids from Rinaldi and Schüth²¹¹. [d] Based on measured cellulose hydrolysis in H₂SO₄ from Saeman⁶⁶. [e] Based on Brønsted acid-catalyzed glucose dehydration from Tan-Soetedjo et al.²¹²

Figure 2 | Depolymerization of lignin in lignocellulosic biomass by the conventional acid hydrolysis. [a] Based on computational studies using model lignin compounds from [a₁]Rinaldi³⁷, [a₂] Kim et al.³⁶, [a₃] Huang et al.²¹³, [a₄] Elder²¹⁴, [a₅] Younker et al.²¹⁵, [a₆] Elder et al.²¹⁶ and [a₇] Elder²¹⁷. [b] Based on a model guaiacyl dimer calculation from Sturgeon et al.³⁸ (3 kcal·mol⁻¹ for carbocation and 11 kcal·mol⁻¹ for double bond). [c] Based on a calculation of the formic acid catalyzed cleavage of a model guaiacyl dimer from Qu et al.¹⁵² *The presented lignin structure is an illustration and does not represent the entire or exact native lignin structure.

Figure 3 | Features and overall mass balances of the main stabilization approaches. a) Functionalities of the reagents and products. b) Overall mass balances of reductive catalytic fractionation (data from Renders et al.¹²⁶). c) Overall mass balances of biomass fractionation with acetal stabilization (adapted from Talebi et al.⁵¹). d) Alcohol stabilization (data taken from Lancefield et al.¹⁶⁶) and e) C2 aldehyde stabilization (data taken from De Santi et al.¹²⁷). Arrow thickness is proportional to the composition and yield of the products.

Figure 4 | Upgrading strategies for lignin and polysaccharide-derived products. a) General approach. Dedicated chemicals refer to bio-based chemicals with no fossil counterpart (see further definitions in the SI). b) Upgrading routes for carbohydrate-based molecules. c) Upgrading routes for lignin-based molecule. Arrow thickness is not proportional to yield.

Figure 5 | Modified 3D Van Krevelen plot and pathways to PTA synthesis starting from both biomass and fossil fuels. The three parameters that define the chemical space are: functional groups density ($F:C$), which characterizes the ratio between carbon and hetero-atoms as well as degree of unsaturation (for a detailed definition of the F parameter see Dusselier et al. and the SI)²¹⁸, number of hydrogens per carbon atom ($H:C$), and molecular weight (Mw). Different subclasses such as biomass derived monomers, petrochemicals, and biorefinery products - all occupy separate areas of the plot, due to their different hydrogen content and functional density. Compounds with low or no functionality and high hydrogen content are petrochemicals (BTX, ethylene, hexane, etc.). Compounds with moderate functionality include both current commodity chemicals and biorefinery products. Finally compounds with the highest functionality and lowest hydrogen content are currently derived from lignocellulose (C_6 and C_5 carbohydrates and G, H, and S lignin monomers).